

Domains of Physical Activity and Psychological Well-being of Secondary Teachers

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ABSTRACT: The study by Trajković et al. (2023) underscores the positive impact of physical activity on psychological well-being, particularly emphasizing its influence on socio-emotional capabilities, life satisfaction, positive emotions, self-worth, confidence, and physical competence. This study extends this understanding by investigating the relationship between different physical activity domains and the psychological well-being of secondary education teachers at Alaminos Integrated National High School in Alaminos, Laguna. Utilizing descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation, the study found that most respondents were aged between 33 and 43, with a notable representation of females. Teachers demonstrated knowledge of various physical activities relevant to their occupation and engaged in activities related to transportation, recognizing the diverse benefits of leisure time and domestic activities on overall well-being. The study examines the relationship between domains of physical activity and psychological well-being, revealing notable correlations across various aspects. In the occupational domain, autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and self-acceptance show significant correlations except for personal growth, while transportation displays a strong and significant relationship with all components of psychological well-being. Similarly, leisure time exhibits a strong correlation with environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relationships, purpose in life, and self-acceptance, but not with autonomy. Likewise, the domestic domain exhibits a strong and significant relationship with all components of psychological well-being. Lastly, these findings shed light on the interconnectedness between domains of physical activity and various aspects of psychological well-being. Thus, the hypothesis positing no significant relationship between these domains was partially rejected.

KEYWORDS: Occupational, Transportation, Leisure Time, Domestic, Psychological Well-Being

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last two decades, physical activity and its determinants have become a critical area of research for various populations. Researchers have now shifted their focus to elucidating the mechanisms that promote physical activity and improved well-being, as Gunnell et al. (2014) mentioned. Physical activity has improved mood and overall psychological well-being, and life satisfaction. It has been demonstrated that increased physical activity benefits both physical and mental health, according to Amlani and Munir (2014). Moreover, physical activity promotion may be a critical strategy for improving mental health globally, given the growing evidence that physical activity benefits mental health and well-being in non-clinical (Rebar and Faulkner et al., 2015). and clinical (Bailey & Hetrick et al., 2017; Rosenbaum, & Tiedemann et al., 2014) populations.

Physical activity (PA), as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), as cited by AL-Johani, (2021), is any bodily movement that requires energy expenditure. Playing, working, utilizing active transportation, completing house chores, and participating in recreational activities are all examples of the different types of activities that can be classified as "physical activity." It is important to note that the term "exercise" is not synonymous with "physical activity." Physical activity has several subcategories, one of which is exercise. Purposely, the goal is to improve or maintain one or more aspects of physical fitness. Exercise is planned, structured, and repetitive, and it is purposeful in this sense because the goal is to either improve or maintain one or more aspects of one's physical fitness. In addition, the World Health Organization (WHO) suggests that adults engage in 150 minutes of moderate physical activity (PA) per week, which includes activities such as leisure time, active transportation, household chores, and work-related activities.

Furthermore, Lapa (2015) cited numerous studies demonstrating that regular physical activity has numerous physical and mental health benefits. Consequently, regular physical activity is a crucial component of a healthy lifestyle. Among the benefits of mental health is psychological well-being. Psychological well-being is typically conceptualized as a combination of positive affective

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states, such as happiness (the hedonic perspective) and optimal functioning in one's personal and social life (the eudaimonic perspective). As stated in summary, "psychological well-being is the state of enjoying life. It is the combination of feeling well and performing well.

According to Ryff and Keyes (1995), as cited by Lapa (2015), psychological well-being is a theoretically grounded instrument focusing on measuring multiple facets of psychological well-being. Positive psychological functioning includes six distinct components. When taken together, these dimensions encompass a breadth of wellness that includes: self-acceptance, positive evaluations of oneself and one's past life; personal growth, a sense of ongoing personal growth and development; purpose in life, the conviction that one's life has meaning and purpose; positive relations with others, the possession of positive relationships with others; environmental mastery; the capacity to manage one's life and the surrounding world effectively; autonomy, and a sense of self-determination.

Indeed, recent research from various countries indicates that teaching is an incredibly stressful profession and that teacher stress is a global phenomenon (Liu & Onwuegbuzie, 2012). As cited by Scheuch et al. (2015), everyday school life is heavily influenced by technological advancements, the increasingly multicultural nature of the social environment, and growing school autonomy. As a result, a more significant portion of teachers' responsibilities will be related to school management and administration. Kunter et al. (2013) stated that the well-being of teachers has a direct bearing on the effectiveness of their instruction and, by extension, their students' academic progress.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The stress experienced by teachers differs significantly from that of individuals in other professions due to the unique demands and responsibilities inherent in teaching roles. Shami et al. (2017) likely argue that factors such as managing diverse student needs, meeting curriculum requirements, and navigating administrative pressures contribute to this distinct form of stress. Moreover, the researcher suggests that despite the prevalence of studies examining well-being in caring professions, such as healthcare, there is a notable gap in research focusing on the well-being of teachers. This study aims to address this gap by exploring the relationship between physical activity and psychological well-being specifically within the context of teaching. The rationale behind this research endeavor lies in the belief that understanding how different domains of physical activity influence the well-being of teachers is essential for developing targeted interventions to support their mental and emotional health.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive- correlational research design, it specifically employed descriptive survey methods in the completion of the study that aimed to identify the challenges in sports participation and coping mechanisms and has these factors relate to student-athletes' achievement. Moreover, the results of the study were the basis for the development of a flexible training program that was helpful to the teacher-coaches of Recto Memorial National High School in facilitating training for student-athletes.

A. Research Instrument

The relevant data for this research were gathered through a researcher-made questionnaire to determine how the respondents perceived domains of physical activity in terms of occupational, transportation, leisure time, and domestic. An adopted with modification psychological well-being (PWB) scale was also used to assess the respondents' perceived level of psychological well-being in terms of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. Experts were consulted to validate the survey questionnaire to ensure that the following set of questions would be reliable in the data-gathering process of this study. This study employed a Likert scale, and respondents were asked to select their responses from the options provided. The surveys were all handed in at the Alaminos Integrated National High School, Division of Laguna, which the researcher personally visited to do so. The researcher's advisers consulted on the question.

B. Research Procedure

The researcher prepared a letter requesting permission from the principal of Alaminos Integrated National High School to conduct the study and distribute the research instrument. After the permission letter was reviewed and approved by the principal, the researcher proceeded with the survey following these steps.

To begin with, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the school's faculty members. They were provided with sufficient time to complete the questionnaire. The researcher waited calmly for the completion of the survey. Following the collection of all the responses, the researcher began tabulating and analyzing the data with the help of her statistician and LSPU San Pablo's Statistic Center. She sent a copy of the data matrix and other supporting documents to ensure the data were statistically treated and correct, particularly when determining the domains of physical activity and psychological well-being.

Descriptive statistics, such as frequency count, mean, and percentage, were considered in the descriptive analysis. To establish a significant relationship, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was applied to assess the connection between the domains of physical activity and psychological well-being among secondary teachers at the 0.05 level of significance.

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III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I. Respondents' Perception on the Domains of Physical Activity in terms of Occupational

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I view doing physical activities as part of work and crave more things and work to do.	4.07	0.71	Agree
2. I do physical activities at work which increases my mood towards my students and colleagues.	3.93	0.77	Agree
3. I exert effort in physical activities at work which I consider rewarding, and I am inspired to continue working throughout the day.	3.93	0.75	Agree
4. I feel productive performing physical activities at work.	3.94	0.78	Agree
5. I do not feel exhausted after a day of work, and still there is quality time with my family.	3.57	1.09	Agree
Overall	3.89	0.69	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 2.50-3.45 Moderately Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 1 presents the perception of the respondents on the domains of physical activity in terms of occupational. The overall mean of 3.89 interpreted as “Agree” indicates that teacher-respondents knew the different physical activities relative to occupational aspect. This also inferred that the respondents have enough information with regard to the essence and importance of physical activities in occupational setup. The results showed that the respondents are optimistic and feel enthusiastic about engaging in physical activities related to their occupation.

This is similar to the study conducted by Post (2019) where he stated that maintaining a positive attitude at work is one of the keys to completing tasks efficiently and improving your entire work experience. Adopting a positive mindset at work increases productivity and personal development by creating a collaborative and supportive environment. You benefit from positivism, as do your clients, coworkers, and staff.

The highest mean of 4.07 interpreted as “Agree” state that most of the respondents do physical activities as part of work and crave more things and work to do. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.57 interpreted as “Agree” states that with regards to physical activity relevant to their occupation, the respondents do not feel exhausted after a day of work, and still there is quality time with my family.

It can be implied that the respondents are eager in doing things or activities relevant to their occupation. In addition, even though they are eager in doing things relative to their occupation, they still make it a point to spend quality time with their family.

The highest mean implies the same findings mentioned in the Virtual College (2022) which states having a positive attitude in the workplace is crucial since it improves both the individual and the working environment. Positive thinkers also see failures as chances to grow and learn, and they can make something positive out of any negative criticism they receive, which helps them feel less stressed out at work. Someone who feels enthusiastic about their profession and seeks out opportunities to learn more is more likely to help others acquire new abilities, resulting in a more skilled workforce.

On the other hand, the lowest mean expresses the essence of work-life balance in an individual's life. It relates to the conversation in CoursEra (2023), wherein it is explained that work-life balance is commonly characterized as the ratio of time spent on work-related activities to time spent on activities that are personally meaningful to you, such as spending time with loved ones or engaging in hobbies and interests outside of work. When work takes more of your time or attention, you will have less time to devote to your other duties or interests. Many people desire to achieve a better balance between their personal and work lives.

However, it can be difficult to achieve in real life. Hard work may occasionally result in more money for family assistance. Your mental health may occasionally deteriorate as a result of your job, draining your energy in interpersonal relationships.

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Table II. Respondents' Perception on the Domains of Physical Activity in terms of Transportation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Walking is simple, effective and cost-effective way of being active.	4.55	0.60	Strongly Agree
2. Active transportation such as walking, cycling, or even using public transit, naturally incorporates physical activity into daily routines.	4.45	0.66	Agree
3. Transportation encourages social interaction, creates a vibrant neighborhood, and increases community cohesion.	4.23	0.74	Agree
4. Transportation provides opportunities to discover local attractions and engage in a more active and enjoyable lifestyle.	4.40	0.62	Agree
5. Transportation does not affect my energy levels, and I am still able to perform many work-related duties.	4.01	0.94	Agree
Overall	4.33	0.58	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

It can be gleaned on Table 2 the perceptions of the respondents on the domains of physical activity in terms of transportation. This part of the study gained an overall mean of 4.33 which can be interpreted as “Agree” which indicates that the teacher-respondents are exposed to different physical activities related to transportation of travelling. The result shows that the teacher-respondents are able to expose themselves to different aspects of physical activities not only in the form of exercising but also in terms of social skills development and discovery.

This result coincides with Active Lives Survey 2017/2018 Year 3 Technical Report published by Ipsos MORI (2019) which states that “transportation” typically refers to physical activity-based travel rather than travel undertaken for recreation. Increasingly, active travel is advocated to increase total physical activity (Csizmadi et al., 2011), with many claimed health benefits (Mueller et al., 2015). Strath et al. (2013) mentioned that transportation options include on-foot travel, bicycle travel, stair climbing and descending to access public transit, and standing while riding public transportation.

The highest mean of 4.55 interpreted as “Strongly Agree” states that walking is simple, effective and cost-effective way of being active. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.01 interpreted as “Agree” states that transportation does not affect the respondents’ energy levels, and they are still able to perform many work-related duties.

It can be elucidated from the highest and lowest mean that the respondents are more into walking as a form of transportation. It may not be in the case of going to school from home and vice versa but as part of their whole day routine in their workplace and that this mode of transportation, walking, is much more beneficial and effective on their part especially that this does not affect the level of their energy in doing their tasks or work-related activities.

The highest mean is being supported by the study of Padmakumar and Patil (2022) which explained that walking is an essential mode of transportation in times of pandemics or natural disasters. Walking optimizes the utilization of our streets and is the most efficient means of transportation in terms of space. A variety of journeys commence and complete with a simple walk. This has long been acknowledged in health research, with walking seen as the foundation for promoting physically active, healthier lifestyles. Walking allows people to easily access jobs, community services, and outdoor places, which promotes a sense of community. On the other hand, the lowest mean reflects the same findings of Cerin et al. (2009) discovered that there was no correlation between the physical activity done while traveling and one's mental well-being, except for those who were obese.

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Table III. Respondents' Perception on the Domains of Physical Activity in terms of Leisure Time

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Leisure activities can increase physical strength and exercise physical fitness.	4.45	0.57	Agree
2. Participating in leisure activities can enhance psychological satisfaction.	4.52	0.61	Strongly Agree
3. Participating in leisure activities helps establish interpersonal relationships.	4.48	0.57	Agree
4. The sense of accomplishment given by leisure activities can relatively boost the sense of work achievement.	4.47	0.59	Agree
5. Leisure activities improve labor productivity.	4.38	0.65	Agree
Overall	4.46	0.55	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

Presented in Table 3 are the perceptions of the respondents on the domains of physical activity in terms of Leisure Time.

An overall mean of 4.46 interpreted as “Agree” depicts that the respondents are aware of the possible effects of having leisure time not only for physical development but also other aspects of human well-being like psychological, social, mental, and emotional well-being. It can also be inferred that involving in different leisure activities helps the respondents to become more active in dealing with their daily living routines.

This result is consistent with the findings of Strath et al. (2013), who noted that individuals occupy their leisure time engaging in volunteer work, sports, interests, and exercise. It has been demonstrated that engaging in recreational sports and other forms of physical activity can help reduce symptoms of depression (Chen et al., 2012) and that doing so is connected with experiencing greater happiness overall (Richards et al., 2015).

The highest mean of 4.52 among the variables is interpreted as “Strongly Agree” states that participating in leisure activities can enhance psychological satisfaction. On the other hand, the variable that gained the lowest mean of 4.38 interpreted as “Agree” states that leisure activities improve labor productivity.

It can be implied that among the variables presented, the respondents put emphasis on the enhancement of psychological satisfaction that they gain in leisure time due to the fact that the majority of the senses are engaged, the respondents are moving their entire bodies in response to the activity, thereby contributing to the development of their holistic personalities. Though still beneficial, the least variable can be explained in a way that clear manifestation that when people engage in leisure activity, it is evident that labor or work productivity is being improved since no work-related is done when doing leisure activity.

The variable with the highest mean is being supported by the study of Shin et.al (2013) which mentioned that relaxing leisure (e.g., viewing television, listening to music) was found to be the strongest positive predictor of coping with stress, while social leisure (e.g., spending time with companions) and cultural leisure (e.g., attending concerts, visiting a museum) significantly predicted greater mental or physical health. Meanwhile, the variable with lowest mean is similar to the study conducted by Ciu et al. (2018) which indicated that leisure exerts a compensatory influence on work and can positively impact labor productivity when it reaches its optimal level of 5,813 hours. However, in situations where leisure time surpasses its optimal value, it can exert a detrimental impact on labor productivity by creating a substitution effect for work.

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Table IV. Respondents' Perception on the Domains of Physical Activity in of Domestic

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I am happy doing household chores, because I consider it a low-cost workout at home.	4.32	0.80	Agree
2. I view doing household chores as a form of exercise that makes me more productive and gives me a greater sense of well-being.	4.45	0.71	Agree
3. I have better cognition, attention span, and physical strength when doing household chores.	4.14	0.86	Agree
4. I feel that doing household chores contributes to my healthy aging and boosts my physical and mental capacity.	4.45	0.71	Agree
5. I do not feel wasted, and I am able to do other things after doing all the household chores.	4.14	0.92	Agree
Overall	4.30	0.68	Agree

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.50-4.49 Agree; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; 1.00-1.49 Strongly Disagree

It can be gleaned on Table 4 the perceptions of the respondents on the domains of physical activity in terms of domestic or housework.

The overall mean of the table, 4.30 interpreted as “Agree”, shows that the respondents are engaged in different domestic or housework activities and that they see it as a form of exercise that enhances their state of well-being. Aside from that, it can also be implied that doing domestic or housework contributes in the development of their daily routines that lead to a better and organized way of spending their time and day.

This finding can be compared to the result of the study posted in World Economic Forum (2021) which states that optimal physical and mental health can be maintained through regular physical activity. Furthermore, it reduces the likelihood of chronic diseases, accidents immobility, dependence, and mortality among the elderly. Engaging in housework as a means of integrating [physical activity] into one's daily routine may result in increased physical activity, which is notably correlated with improved functional health, particularly among older individuals residing in the community. Also, Hu et al. (2023) found that individuals whose household activity levels were somewhat lower had a 60% increased risk of dying from any cause in comparison to those whose activity levels were relatively higher. The housework may improve older people's cognitive function, which is associated with better health and longer life expectancy.

The variables with the highest mean of 4.45, interpreted as “Agree”, state that “I view doing household chores as a form of exercise that makes me more productive and gives me a greater sense of well-being.” and “I feel that doing household chores contributes to my healthy aging and boosts my physical and mental capacity.” On the other hand, the variables with the lowest mean of 4.14 which is interpreted as “Agree” cite that “I have better cognition, attention span, and physical strength when doing household chores.” and “I do not feel wasted, and I am able to do other things after doing all the household chores.”

The variables with the highest mean infer that aside from doing housework as a prime duty in the family, the respondents also see it as a way on how they can improve their holistic well-being covering all aspect of human development. Meanwhile, the variables with the least mean imply that somehow, these variables are given the least importance or attention as they perform different housework activities.

The variables with the highest mean share the same view with Strath et al. (2013) who mentioned that domestic physical activities include cleaning the house, working in the yard, taking care of children, performing self-care tasks, going shopping, and other incidental activities. However, Richards et al. (2015) found that engaging in "a lot" of domestic physical activity was the activity most significantly correlated with self-reported happiness across all physical activity domains (as measured by a single question from the SF-36 Health Survey questionnaire). In addition, Garcia (2019) stated that engaging in household tasks such as organizing and cleaning can contribute to anxiety reduction and promote a feeling of control. Consequently, doing chores can also effectively alleviate stress. Moreover, this is a significant triumph as stress may adversely affect all aspects of well-being, including the cognitive functioning of our minds.

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Meanwhile, the variables with the least mean agree with the discussion of Chu et al. (2023) stating that mental health acted as a partial mediator in the association between housework and survival. As previously stated, housework may increase the amount of physical activity performed by an individual, and physical activity has been associated with a protective effect on mental health.

Table V. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Autonomy

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I am not afraid to voice out my opinion even it opposes the perspective stand of most people.	4.97	0.92	Moderately Agree
2. I have my own decisions and do not usually influence by what everyone else is doing.	5.18	0.54	Moderately Agree
3. I have confidence in my opinions even if they are contrary to the general consensus.	5.13	0.62	Moderately Agree
4. I am happy with myself and it is more important than the approval of other people on me.	5.42	0.67	Moderately Agree
5. I do not tend to worry about what other people think of me.	5.02	0.98	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.14	0.55	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

It can be gleaned from Table 5 the perceptions of the respondents on their level of psychological well-being in terms of autonomy. The overall mean of 5.14 interpreted as “Moderately Agree” implies that the respondents have their own means of expressing their point of view in whatever instance or situation they are exposed to and that they can express those freely without hesitation, even if sometimes it negates the ideas and opinions of other people.

This result coincides with the study of Chan et al. (2019), which explained that positive and healthy well-being is the foundation of autonomy, which empowers an individual to resist social and personal pressures to think critically and make prudent decisions, as well as to evaluate themselves in accordance with the standards they have established for themselves.

The variable with the highest mean of 5.42, which is interpreted as “Moderately Agree” states, “I am happy with myself and it is more important than the approval of other people on me.” Meanwhile, the variable with the lowest mean of 4.97, described as “Moderately Agree” states that “I am not afraid to voice out my opinion, even it opposes the perspective stand of most people.”

It can be inferred that the respondents value more the individual happiness that they can have rather than the commendations and comments that they will receive from other people. It is also inferred that they are quite hesitant to make a stand with their views. This is aligned with the study of Hansenne (2021), which confirmed that putting positivity first is linked to well-being; it has a little negative correlation with depressive symptoms and a moderate positive correlation with psychological well-being, life satisfaction, and subjective happiness. In addition, it is also being supported by Zhao et al. (2019), who mentioned that when people are in an interdependent position, prioritizing pleasure can enhance their well-being, particularly for those who are less likely to embrace their inner experiences.

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Table VI. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Environmental Mastery

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I am quite good at managing different responsibilities in my daily life.	5.19	0.64	Moderately Agree
2. I generally do a good job of taking care of my personal finances and affairs.	5.19	0.77	Moderately Agree
3. I am good at managing my time, so that I can accomplish all the things to be done.	5.15	0.74	Moderately Agree
4. I was able to build a home and a lifestyle for myself that fit my liking.	5.18	0.60	Moderately Agree
5. I fit very well with the people and the community around me.	5.09	0.71	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.16	0.58	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

Table 6 shows the respondents' perceptions of their psychological well-being in terms of environmental mastery.

The overall mean of 5.16, interpreted as "Moderately Agree" means that the respondents can create a well-planned environment for themselves where they have arranged time schedules, finances, work-life balance, and good social relationships with other people in the community or environment where they are.

This result is clearly supported by the study of Chan et al. (2019), who described how people had control over a variety of complex activities and events, as well as the complexity of their life courses, and that they were able to show mastery and competence in managing the external environment by taking advantage of opportunities. People who find themselves in such circumstances could make the most of a scenario that is good for them. Despite the chaos, obstacles, and difficulties that life throws at them, they can keep moving forward toward their life's purpose and goals. Healthy psychological well-being can be demonstrated by an individual who ultimately masters the external world. It implies that an individual is in charge of every circumstance he or she is put into. The variables that gained the highest mean of 5.19, interpreted as "Moderately Agree" state that "I am quite good at managing different responsibilities in my daily life." and "I generally do a good job of taking care of my personal finances and affairs." On the other hand, the variable with the least mean of 5.09, described as "Moderately Agree" states that "I fit very well with the people and the community around me."

These variables can imply that the respondents are well-equipped with skills in dealing with all responsibilities given to them as well as in managing finances and affairs relative to them. On the other hand, the variable that gained the least mean may imply that the respondents are doing their best in trying to fit in and becoming a part of the community that they are in.

It can be linked to the discussion of Garcia et al. (2023) about personal management. It was mentioned that having emotional, mental, and behavioral control is a key component of personal management, or self-management abilities. You can create separate goals and take action to achieve them if you possess this skill. In the long run, personal management abilities assist in guiding one's career path. Additionally, personal management abilities were mentioned as a factor that individuals must acquire to be effective in this regard. Communication abilities, effective time management, organizational skills, goal setting, adaptability, collaboration, accountability, and self-motivation are examples of such abilities.

Furthermore, the outcome is also associated with the article published in Motion Blog (2023), which defines the techniques and strategies individuals use to maintain a balance between their personal and professional lives as self-management skills. These abilities can assist you in efficiently managing and governing your thoughts, feelings, and actions in various situations. Furthermore, experts assert that self-management skills hold significant importance. They enhance efficiency and alleviate stress, among other advantages. Being conscious of your emotions and behaviors enables you to be more prepared to manage the requirements and difficulties of your personal and professional spheres. Additionally, it aids in preserving consciousness, enabling you to make more intelligent selections.

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Table VII. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Personal Growth

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about the world.	5.49	0.55	Moderately Agree
2. I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time.	5.36	0.63	Moderately Agree
3. I am interested in activities that will expand my horizons.	5.41	0.62	Moderately Agree
4. I want to try new ways of developing myself personally and professionally.	5.45	0.62	Moderately Agree
5. I do enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old, familiar ways of doing things.	5.18	0.72	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.38	0.54	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

Table 7 provides details on the respondents' perceptions of their psychological well-being in terms of personal growth.

The overall mean of 5.38, verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree” implies that the respondents are open to experiencing new challenges and interesting things that will offer them personal and professional development as well as a widening of opportunities by engaging in new situations, which will make them modify or change their old version to cope with the newest trends that the world offers.

The study by Chan et al. (2019) clearly supports this result. It is explained that people who have healthy psychological well-being perceive every chance and opportunity as a challenge to become the best versions of themselves. Realizing their potential is a source of inspiration for them, propelling them to other stages of development, expansion, and growth. When people step beyond their comfort zones and make use of their talents and potential, it opens the door to the possibility of furthering their personal growth and development. A sign of a healthy mind is seeing and acknowledging your own progress, which leads to positive and helpful life functions.

The variable with the highest mean of 5.49, interpreted as “Moderately Agree” states that “I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about the world.” Meanwhile, the variable with the lowest mean of 5.18, described as “Moderately Agree” cites that “I do enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old, familiar ways of doing things.”

It can be inferred that, with consideration of the mean scores, the respondents are eager to try and test their capacity and capability to convey meaning about what they see and experience by trying out new things. While the variable that gained the lowest mean may imply that the respondents are quite hesitant or afraid to let go of the things that they have learned before experiencing new things.

According to Ackerman (2017), self-expression is the act of expressing oneself, and it can happen in a variety of ways. You can communicate your authentic inner self through various means, including words, actions, possessions, facial expressions, body language, gestures, and attire. It seems that not all individuals comprehend the profound importance of self-expression, notwithstanding the concept's apparent simplicity. It seems that not all individuals comprehend the profound importance of self-expression, notwithstanding the concept's apparent simplicity. We are constantly receiving messages about how we ought to behave, think, talk, and look; who to associate with; what to drink, consume, study, and do for enjoyment; whom to adore or dislike; and, most importantly, who we ought to become.

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Table VIII. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Positive Relations

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I feel that most people see me as loving and affectionate.	4.90	0.68	Moderately Agree
2. I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members or friends.	5.52	0.66	Moderately Agree
3. I feel that people would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.	5.16	0.68	Moderately Agree
4. I know that I can trust my friends and they know that they can trust me.	5.40	0.69	Moderately Agree
5. I do not feel lonely because I have a lot of close friends with whom to share my concerns.	5.35	0.66	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.27	0.54	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

It can be gleaned from Table 8 the perceptions of the respondents on their level of psychological well-being in terms of positive relations.

The overall mean for positive relations is 5.27, verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree” implies that the respondents possess positive relationships with other people. It is manifested through the manner in which they interact with each other developed by having personal and mutual conversations and by becoming a giving person to all who are always willing to do things for the benefit of all. In addition, the respondents also believe that the positive relationship they have is grounded in trust with each of the people around them, as well as because of their love and affection.

Chan et al. (2019) classified a satisfying relationship with others as one that is warm, empathic, affectionate, and close to each other. Building a connection on trust ensures a healthy balance between giving and receiving. A meaningful relationship with family, co-workers, friends, and others demonstrates good psychological well-being. Spending quality time together and staying in touch even during challenging times demonstrates this.

“I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members or friends” is the variable that gained the highest mean of 5.52, interpreted as “Moderately Agree”. On the other hand, the variable that gets the lowest mean of 5.16, verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree”, states that “I feel that people would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others.”

It can be inferred from the responses of the respondents that, in order to foster positive relations with other people, it is clear that they rely on communication as the most effective means of establishing harmonious relationships, particularly with family and friends. Meanwhile, it's clear that people view them as individuals who can set aside time to build relationships with others.

This pertains to Pennock (2023), who asserts that effective communication facilitates the expression of individuals' thoughts, emotions, and demands, thereby cultivating a more profound comprehension and camaraderie among them. Clear and transparent communication can foster harmony and satisfaction in a relationship by addressing difficulties and solving conflicts. Moreover, Better Health Channel (2014) posted on their website an article elucidating that communication plays a crucial role in relationships by enabling one to convey their feelings and needs. Engaging in communication not only facilitates the fulfilment of basic needs but also fosters a sense of rapport within the relationship.

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Table IX. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Purpose in Life

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I am an active person in carrying out the plans I set for myself.	5.23	0.67	Moderately Agree
2. I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality.	5.41	0.64	Moderately Agree
3. I have a good sense of what it is I am trying to accomplish in life.	5.41	0.58	Moderately Agree
4. I always set goals for myself; for me, it is not a waste of time.	5.36	0.71	Moderately Agree
5. I always feel like I've done everything there is to do in life.	5.02	0.83	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.29	0.57	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

Table 9 presents the perceptions of the respondents on their level of psychological well-being in terms of purpose in life. The overall mean of the variables regarding purpose in life is marked at 5.29, which is verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree”. This suggests that the respondents possess a clear understanding of their life plans and have established specific goals and timelines that they are solely responsible for achieving. Moreover, this also shows that the respondents tend to become optimistic and active individuals in actualizing their plans and by doing all the possible things to do so that they will be able to attain their plans.

It is similar to the study of Chan et al. (2019) which defined purpose as the sense of life direction determined by one's beliefs and goals. People realize that life on earth is a journey with a destination. A person's goals and objectives drive them to work hard, passionately, and tirelessly until they reach their goals and objectives.

The variables “I enjoy making plans for the future and working to make them a reality” and “I have a good sense of what it is I am trying to accomplish in life” received the highest mean of 5.41, which is verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree”. Meanwhile, the variable “I always feel like I've done everything there is to do in life” gets the lowest mean of 5.02, interpreted as “Moderately Agree”.

It can be inferred from the responses of the respondents that they are optimistic about realizing their goals and plans for the future and have a concrete way of putting these things into action. It can also be inferred that even though the respondents are making all the efforts they can, they still think or reflect that they have not been doing their best or that there are better things that they can do, making the variable with the lowest mean noticeable in terms of the garnered mean.

This coincides with what Riopel (2019) cited: that goals have a dual impact on both behavior and job performance. They also serve to activate and direct energy, resulting in increased overall effort. Greater exertion results in enhanced persistence. Goals serve as a source of motivation for us to create effective tactics that will allow us to achieve the desired level of performance. Achieving a goal can result in satisfaction and heightened motivation, whereas failing to reach the goal can lead to dissatisfaction and reduced motivation. In addition, Dunn (2020) provided a comprehensive guide outlining the specific actions individuals might take to achieve the goals they have established: (1) Size is important. Great achievements often result from small steps taken; (2) Determine what aspect of this objective is most significant to you; (3) Obstacles. Both tangible and conceptual. What obstacles are possible to arise? How do you envision yourself accomplishing this objective? Identify your areas of weakness; (4) View your life as if you've accomplished that objective; (5) Be accountable and exposed.

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Table X. Respondents' Perception on their Level of Psychological Well-Being in terms of Self-acceptance

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. I have made some mistakes in the past but feel that all in all everything had worked out for the best.	5.28	0.79	Moderately Agree
2. Even if there have been ups and downs in the past, I wouldn't want to change.	5.03	0.75	Moderately Agree
3. When I compare myself with friends and acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am.	4.93	1.05	Moderately Agree
4. In general, I feel confident and positive about myself.	4.93	1.05	Moderately Agree
5. I think that my attitude towards myself is probably as positive as most people feel about themselves.	5.28	0.71	Moderately Agree
Overall	5.09	0.66	Moderately Agree

Legend: 5.60-6.00 Strongly Agree; 4.60-5.59 Moderately Agree; 3.60-4.59 Slightly Agree; 2.60-3.59 Slightly Disagree; 1.60-2.59 Moderately Disagree; 1.00-1.59 Strongly Disagree

It can be gleaned on Table 10 the perceptions of the respondents on their level of psychological well-being in terms of Self-Acceptance.

The overall mean of the variables under Self-Acceptance is marked at 5.09, interpreted as “Moderately Agree”. This implies that the respondents are aware of how they interact with other people and that they are knowledgeable about the mistakes that they have made. Based on their responses, it can also be derived that they are not into changing themselves just because they experienced life’s challenges. Most importantly, this also means that the respondents have a positive attitude and outlook towards themselves.

The results express the same ideas stated in the study of Chan et al. (2019), which argued that recognizing and embracing that everyone, including oneself, has numerous features, including both negative and positive qualities, produces happiness and satisfaction. Therefore, a positive attitude toward oneself helps develop good psychological well-being, allowing individuals to perform efficiently and with purpose.

The variables “I have made some mistakes in the past but feel that all in all everything has worked out for the best” and “I think that my attitude towards myself is probably as positive as most people feel about themselves” get the highest mean of 5.28, interpreted as “Moderately Agree”. On the other hand, the variables “When I compare myself with friends and acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am” and “In general, I feel confident and positive about myself” obtained the lowest mean of 4.93, which are verbally interpreted as “Moderately Agree”.

Based on the highest and lowest means under self-acceptance, it can be inferred that the respondents always think positively toward themselves, even though they sometimes make bad choices. In addition, since they know themselves very well, it can also be noted that they think that they are superior or better than other people and always choose to accept how well they interact with other people.

This implication is grounded on the belief of Morgado et.al (2014) that self-acceptance can be defined as having the ability to acknowledge and embrace one's strengths and weaknesses without making judgments. Additionally, it includes the ability to completely understand oneself and identify areas in which one excels and struggles. In connection to this, Gupta (2022) suggested strategies that will help an individual accept himself. These strategies are as follows: (1) accept your values; (2) establish healthy boundaries; (3) make amends with yourself; (4) avoid self-blame; (5) avoid making comparisons; (6) concentrate on the positive; (7) maintain a journal; (8) practice loving-kindness meditation; and (9) seek assistance.

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Table XI. Test of Relationship between Domains of Physical Activity and Psychological Well-Being

<i>Domains of Physical Activity</i>	<i>Psychological Well-being</i>					
	<i>Autonomy</i>	<i>Environmental mastery</i>	<i>Personal growth</i>	<i>Positive relationship</i>	<i>Purpose in life</i>	<i>Self-acceptance</i>
Occupational	.308**	.341**	0.161	.218*	.382**	.465**
Transportation	.360**	.468**	.505**	.438**	.461**	.510**
Leisure Time	0.135	.358**	.544**	.340**	.300**	.389**
Domestic	.409**	.371**	.449**	.459**	.439**	.546**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It can be gleaned from Table 11 the test for significant relationship between domains of Physical Activity and components of Psychological Well-being. In terms of Occupational Domain compared to the components of Psychological Well-Being, it showed a strong significant relationship with the components: autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. In addition, the occupational domain also exhibited a slight or weak significant relationship with the component: positive relationship with others. Meanwhile, the occupational domain showed no significant relationship with personal growth as a component of psychological well-being.

Furthermore, Leisure, as a domain of physical activity, exhibited a strong significant relationship with all the components of psychological well-being except for autonomy, where it did not show any significant relationship at all.

Lastly, the domains Transportation and Domestic have demonstrated a strong significant relationship to all the components of psychological well-being.

It can be elucidated from the result that the domains of physical activity have direct effects on the psychological well-being of the respondents. This means that as the respondents engage in different kinds of physical activity, they inhibit different values and lessons that are directly connected to any of the components considered to be part of total development, thus making an impact on how they act and interact with other people in the community as they perform any physical activity. These learnings that they gained from experience then shaped them as individuals in all aspects of their lives as to the different attributes presented in this study.

These identified significant relationships coincide with the study of Trajković et al. (2023), which mentioned that engaging in exercise and physical activity positively influences numerous psychological constructs, such as the development of individuals' socioemotional capabilities, life satisfaction, positive emotions, self-worth, confidence in oneself, and physical competence. A protective factor for lower stress levels and stress attitudes, depression, bad eating habits, and exercise habits, physical activity may be seen as a significant element in preventing these negative outcomes. Higher levels of physical exercise have been related to a number of health benefits, including reduced levels of the stress hormone cortisol, a reduction in negative mood, fewer symptoms of anxiety and depression, and enhanced sleep quality.

In addition, the Mental Health Foundation (2021) suggested in an article that engaging in physical activity has a significant potential to improve our general well-being. Even a brief burst of ten minutes of brisk walking increases our mental alertness, energy, and positive mood. Regularly engaging in physical activity has the potential to boost our self-esteem while simultaneously lowering our levels of tension and anxiety. Additionally, it contributes to the overall improvement of the quality of life for individuals who are dealing with mental health issues, as well as the prevention of the development of mental health problems. Furthermore, Benlidayi (2023) also suggested that physical activity may have a mediating effect on psychological health by way of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. The HPA axis is a complex system involving interactions between the hypothalamus, pituitary gland, and adrenal glands. It plays a crucial role in regulating stress responses and various bodily functions. Exercising can lead to better sleep, which in turn can contribute to improvements in mood and cognition.

Moreover, leisure activities, as a domain of physical activity, have no significant relationship with autonomy. This aligns with Fancourt et al., 2021, who noted that leisure, as a domain of physical activity, is frequently associated with providing individuals the opportunity to exercise autonomy. However, the study discovered that there was no significant relationship between leisure activities and autonomy. This calls into question the notion that leisure activities necessarily foster autonomy. This finding suggests that other factors may play a more significant role in determining the level of autonomy experienced during leisure activities. One possible reason for this lack of a significant relationship could be that individuals have limited choice when selecting their leisure activities. External factors such as time constraints, financial limitations, or social commitments may hinder individuals from engaging in activities of their preference (Duncan et al., 2017).

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On the other hand, there was no significant relationship between the occupational field and personal growth as a part of psychological well-being. This coincides with the study by Buecker et al. (2020), which stated that one possible explanation for the absence of a significant relationship between occupational physical activity and personal growth, a facet of psychological well-being, is that typical views of work primarily emphasize job-related skills and career growth. However, personal growth also involves learning more about oneself and maturing as an individual, not merely advancing in one's career. Thus, typical views on physical activity in the workplace may fail to consider the broader aspects of personal growth. We need to look at things like work-life balance, chances to learn new skills at work, and how good work experiences can make us feel more in control of our lives, in order to fully understand how work affects personal growth.

IV. CONCLUSION

The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between domains of physical activity and psychological well-being was partially rejected.

Based on the findings and conclusions made, it is recommended that schools design a more effective and engaging school improvement plan and teacher programs that consider teachers' performance, focusing on the different domains of physical activity to ensure their psychological health and holistic development. Teachers should conduct self-assessments of their psychological well-being and devise ways to improve their state while engaging in the physical activities required by their profession, particularly as educators. Furthermore, future researchers should conduct additional studies relevant to this subject matter to fully substantiate the significant findings and address the gaps identified in this study.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Gunnell, K. E., Crocker, P. R. E., Mack, D. E., Wilson, P. M., & Zumbo, B. D. (2014). Goal contents, motivation, psychological need satisfaction, well-being and physical activity: A test of self-determination theory over 6 months. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 15(1), 19–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2013.08.005>
- 2) Amlani, N. M., & Munir, F. (2014). Does Physical Activity Have an Impact on Sickness Absence? A Review. *Sports Medicine*, 44(7), 887–907. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-014-0171-0>
- 3) Rebar, A. L., Faulkner, G., & Stanton, R. (2015). An exploratory study examining the core affect hypothesis of the anti-depressive and anxiolytic effects of physical activity. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 9, 55–58.

Domains of Physical Activity and Psychological Well-being of Secondary Teachers

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2015.10.001>

- 4) Bailey, A. P., Hetrick, S. E., Rosenbaum, S., Purcell, R., & Parker, A. G. (2017). Treating depression with physical activity in adolescents and young adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials. *Psychological Medicine*, 48(7), 1068–1083. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0033291717002653>
- 5) Rosenbaum, S., Tiedemann, A., Sherrington, C., Curtis, J., & Ward, P. B. (2014). Physical activity interventions for people with mental illness: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 18, e150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2014.11.161>
- 6) Lapa, T. Y. (2015). Physical Activity Levels and Psychological Well-Being: A Case Study of University Students. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 186, 739–743. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.122>
- 7) Ryff, C. D., & Keyes, C. L. M. (1995). The structure of psychological well-being revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719–727. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.69.4.719>
- 8) Liu, S., & Onwuegbuzie, A. J. (2012). Chinese teachers' work stress and their turnover intention. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 53, 160–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2012.03.006>
- 9) Scheuch, K., Haufe, E., & Seibt, R. (2015). Teachers' Health. *Deutsches Aerzteblatt Online*. <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2015.0347>
- 10) Kunter, M., Klusmann, U., Baumert, J., Richter, D., Voss, T., & Hachfeld, A. (2013). Professional competence of teachers: Effects on instructional quality and student development. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 105(3), 805–820. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0032583>
- 11) Shami, R., Tareh, M., & Taran, H. (2017). Identifying the relationship among teacher's mental health and emotional intelligence and their burnout. *Independent Journal of Management & Production*, 8(1), 124–143. <https://doi.org/10.14807/ijmp.v8i1.513>
- 12) Post, J. (2019, October). Why a Positive Attitude in the Workplace Matters. *Business News Daily*. <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/6912-develop-positive-mindset.html>
- 13) How to Demonstrate a Positive Attitude at Work | Virtual College. (n.d.). www.virtual-college.co.uk. <https://www.virtualcollege.co.uk/resources/demonstrate-positive-attitude-at-work>
- 14) Coursera. (2023, June 15). Work-Life Balance: What It Is and How to Achieve It. Coursera. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/work-life-balance>
- 15) Csizmadi, I., Lo Siou, G., Friedenreich, C. M., Owen, N., & Robson, P. J. (2011). Hours spent and energy expended in physical activity domains: Results from The Tomorrow Project cohort in Alberta, Canada. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 8(1), 110. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-8-110>
- 16) Strath, S. J., Kaminsky, L. A., Ainsworth, B. E., Ekelund, U., Freedson, P. S., Gary, R. A., Richardson, C. R., Smith, D. T., & Swartz, A. M. (2013). Guide to the Assessment of Physical Activity: Clinical and Research Applications. *Circulation*, 128(20), 2259–2279. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.0000435708.67487.da>
- 17) Padmakumar, A., & Patil, G. R. (2022). COVID-19 effects on urban driving, walking, and transit usage trends: Evidence from Indian metropolitan cities. *Cities*, 126, 103697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2022.103697>
- 18) Cerin, E., Leslie, E., Sugiyama, T., & Owen, N. (2009). Associations of multiple physical activity domains with mental well-being. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 2(2), 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhpa.2009.09.004>
- 19) Chen, L.-J., Stevinson, C., Ku, P.-W., Chang, Y.-K., & Chu, D.-C. (2012). Relationships of leisure-time and non-leisure-time physical activity with depressive symptoms: a population-based study of Taiwanese older adults. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 9(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1479-5868-9-28>
- 20) Richards, J., Jiang, X., Kelly, P., Chau, J., Bauman, A., & Ding, D. (2015). Don't worry, be happy: cross-sectional associations between physical activity and happiness in 15 European countries. *BMC Public Health*, 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-1391-4>
- 21) Shin, K., & You, S. (2013). Leisure Type, Leisure Satisfaction and Adolescents' Psychological Wellbeing. *Journal of Pacific Rim Psychology*, 7(2), 53–62. <https://doi.org/10.1017/prp.2013.6>
- 22) Cui, D., Wei, X., Wu, D., Cui, N., & Nijkamp, P. (2018). A Service of zbw Leibniz-Informationszentrum Wirtschaft Leibniz Information Centre for Economics. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/183126/1/1032556382.pdf>
- 23) How housework can improve our mental and physical health. (n.d.). World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/12/housework-linked-to-sharper-memory-in-older-adults/>
- 24) Hu, L., Wang, L., Zhang, Y., Wang, K., Wang, Y., Tan, H., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Participation in Household Physical Activity Lowers Mortality Risk in Chinese Women and Men. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(2), 987–987. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20020987>
<https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.0000435708.67487.da>

Domains of Physical Activity and Psychological Well-being of Secondary Teachers

- 25) Garcia, R., Lagace, L., Herrity, J., Eads, A. (2019). Personal Management Skills (With Definition and Examples). Indeed. <https://ca.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/personal-management-skills>
- 26) Chu, L., Gong, X., Lay, J. C., Zhang, F., Fung, H. H., & Kwok, T. (2023). The perks of doing housework: Longitudinal associations with survival and underlying mechanisms. *BMC Geriatrics*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-023-04039-1>
- 27) Ipsos MORI. (2019). <https://sportengland-production-files.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/active-lives-survey-full-y3-technical-note-apr-2019.pdf>
<https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.0000435708.67487.da>
- 28) Chan, D. W., Chan, L., & Sun, X. (2019). Developing a Brief Version of Ryff's Scale to Assess the Psychological Well-Being of Adolescents in Hong Kong. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 35(3), 414–422. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759/a000403>
- 29) Hansenne, M. (2021). Valuing Happiness is Not a Good Way of Pursuing Happiness, but Prioritizing Positivity is: A Replication Study. *Psychologica Belgica*, 61(1), 306–314. <https://doi.org/10.5334/pb.1036>
- 30) Zhao, H., Zhang, H., Xu, Y., He, W., & Lu, J. (2019). Why Are People High in Dispositional Awe Happier? The Roles of Meaning in Life and Materialism. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01208>
- 31) Motion Blog. (2023, October 6). 11 Self-Management Skills and How to Develop Them. [www.usemotion.com.https://www.usemotion.com/blog/self-management-skills](https://www.usemotion.com/blog/self-management-skills)
- 32) Ackerman, C. (2017, August 4). Theory of Positive Disintegration 101: On Becoming Your Authentic Self. [PositivePsychology.com. https://positivepsychology.com/dabrowskis-positive-disintegration/](https://positivepsychology.com/dabrowskis-positive-disintegration/)
- 33) Pennock, S. F. (2023, September 6). Harmony: The Key to Healthy Couples Communication. [Quenza. https://quenza.com/blog/knowledge-base/couples-communication/](https://quenza.com/blog/knowledge-base/couples-communication/)
- 34) Department of Health. (2014). Relationships and communication. Better Health; Victoria State Government. <https://www.betterhealth.vic.gov.au/health/healthyliving/relationships-and-communication>
- 35) Riopel, L. (2019, June 14). The importance, benefits, and value of goal setting. *Positive Psychology*. <https://positivepsychology.com/benefits-goal-setting/>
- 36) Dunn, A. (2020, January 10). Actualizing Your Goals. 5 Steps to Success. Ali Dunn. <https://www.alidunn.com/blog/2020/1/9/goal-setting-2020>
- 37) Morgado, F. F. da R., Betanho Campana, A. N. N., & Fernandes Tavares, M. da C. G. C. (2014). Development and Validation of the Self-Acceptance Scale for Persons with Early Blindness: The SAS-EB. *PLoS ONE*, 9(9), e106848. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0106848>
- 38) Gupta, S. (2022, September 14). What Is Self-Acceptance? *Verywell Mind*; Dotdash Media, Inc. <https://www.verywellmind.com/self-acceptance-characteristics-importance-and-tips-for-improvement-6544468>
- 39) Trajković, N., Mitić, P., Barić, R., Bogataj, S. (2023). Editorial: Effects of physical activity on psychological well-being. *PubMed Cental*. 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1121976
- 40) Mental Health Foundation. (2023). How to look after your mental health using exercise. [www.mentalhealth.org.uk. https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/explore-mental-health/publications/how-look-after-your-mental-health-using-exercise#:~:text=Physical%20activity%20has%20a%20huge](https://www.mentalhealth.org.uk/explore-mental-health/publications/how-look-after-your-mental-health-using-exercise#:~:text=Physical%20activity%20has%20a%20huge)
- 41) Benlidayi, I. (2023). THE EFFECTS OF EXERCISING ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING IN OLDER ADULTS. *Anti-Aging Eastern Europe*, 2(1), 36-41. <https://doi.org/10.56543/aaeeu.2023.2.1.06>
- 42) Fancourt, D., Aughterson, H., Finn, S., Walker, E., & Steptoe, A. (2021). How leisure activities affect health: a narrative review and multi-level theoretical framework of mechanisms of action. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 8(4), 329–339. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366\(20\)30384-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2215-0366(20)30384-9)
- 43) Duncan, J. M., Withers, M. C., Lucier-Greer, M., Ferraro, A. J., & Reed-Fitzke, K. (2017). Research note: social leisure engagement, peer support, and depressive symptomology among emerging adults. *Leisure Studies*, 37(3), 343–351. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614367.2017.1411968>
- 44) Buecker, S., Simacek, T., Ingwersen, B., Terwiel, S., & Simonsmeier, B. A. (2020). Physical Activity and Subjective well-being in Healthy individuals: a meta-analytic Review. *Health Psychology Review*, 15(4), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17437199.2020.1760728>